

Political Studies Book Note Form

Thank you for offering to review:

Anthony F. Heath, Stephen D. Fisher, Gemma Rosenblatt, David Sanders, and Maria Sobolewska (2013) *The Political Integration of Ethnic Minorities in Britain*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 256pp, £55.00 (h/b), ISBN 9780199656639

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Thank you for agreeing to write for *Political Studies Review* and enriching the development of information in political science.

The Political Integration of Ethnic Minorities in Britain offers an encouraging picture of how Britain's minorities are 'just as good democrats as other British citizens' (p205). The key finding of the research carried out by Anthony Heath and his colleagues is that engagement in both the electoral process and other forms of political participation does not differ significantly between ethnic minorities and the white majority. Particularly for the second generation, the trend is for a convergence with the rest of society. This is not to say that there is nothing specific about ethnic minority political engagement. There is evidence to show that ethnicity does in fact trump class when looking at allegiance to the Labour Party. Indeed, minorities are, in general, less supportive of government spending but still more inclined to vote Labour. The data from the Ethnic Minority British Election Survey (EMBES) throws up some other interesting results. For example, minorities were less likely to abstain or defect from Labour at the 2010 general election. The authors explore these and other issues in detail and attempt to provide possible reasons for certain findings without discounting alternative explanations.

The book is divided into ten chapters and looks at several key topics including: whether there is an ethnic minority agenda and how/if this is incorporated into mainstream politics; why Labour partisanship is so much more prevalent among minorities; rates of registration, turnout, abstention and defection; forms of non-electoral participation and overall satisfaction with democracy and its institutions. In each chapter the data is presented in a manner designed to not bamboozle the non-specialist reader who is guided through the results with the most significant findings highlighted and commented upon. Handily for those who wish to get more intimate with the data, supplementary tables are provided in the appendices of several chapters. Heath *et al* should also be commended for recognising the potential flaws and limitations with their survey data. They are at pains to warn readers about the pitfalls of inferring causal processes from the statistics and readily admit to the fuzziness of some of the ethnic categories they are using.

The recent media interest in the potential of ethnic minorities to significantly influence the next UK general election in 2015 means that the timing of this book is impeccable. It should give serious pause for thought for politicians and political parties, in particular Labour, which despite successfully incorporating minorities in the past is in danger of taking their loyalty for granted.

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